

Side-Effects of Zermelo's Axioms

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Abstract

In Zermelo's system of axioms Z , and also in ZF the set of all natural numbers \mathbb{N} is based on *Axiom of Infinity*. Without this axiom the set \mathbb{N} cannot be established. But from then on the set \mathbb{N} can be built, rebuilt or dismantle up to the empty set in some other ways, as well. It leads to contradiction. Points below.

Ernst Zermelo's system of axioms is presented in [1] in German and also in English as the verbatim English translation. The entry point for us is the version of axioms available in [2].

1 Introduction

Let \mathbb{N} be the set of all natural numbers and $\mathbb{P}(\mathbb{N})$ be the powerset of the set \mathbb{N} i.e. the set of all subsets of \mathbb{N} . No matter whether \mathbb{N} is introduced as the least inductive set or as the first non-zero limit ordinal ω . It is enough that \mathbb{N} exists.

- \mathcal{A} is the family of all one-element subsets of \mathbb{N} :

$$\mathcal{A} = \{ X \in \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{N}) \mid (X \neq \emptyset) \wedge [(n \in X) \wedge (m \in X) \Rightarrow (n = m)] \}.$$

Then

$$\bigcup \mathcal{A} = \mathbb{N}.$$

- Let i be an ordinary identity:

$$i : \mathbb{N} \longrightarrow \mathbb{N};$$

$$\mathbb{N} \ni n \longrightarrow i(n) = n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Then

$$i(\mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{N}.$$

- Let j be an identity defined by induction:

$$j : \mathbb{N} \longrightarrow \mathbb{N};$$

$$j(n) = \begin{cases} n & \text{for } n = 0, \\ (j(n-1)) + 1 & \text{for } n \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

Then

$$j(\mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{N}.$$

and this set – the set $j(\mathbb{N})$ – is built by induction. As $j(\mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{N}$, in Z and in ZF the set \mathbb{N} can be built (or rebuilt) by induction.

All three sets: $j(\mathbb{N}), i(\mathbb{N}), \bigcup \mathcal{A}$ are not the immediate consequence of *Axiom of Infinity*.

2 Core

Let us define the inductive function g as follows:

$$g : \mathbb{N} \longrightarrow \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{N});$$

$$g(n) = \begin{cases} \{n\} & \text{for } n = 0, \\ g(n-1) \cup \{n\} & \text{for } n \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

We can notice that $g(n) = \bigcup_{i=0}^n \{i\}$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and it is a beginning segment of \mathbb{N} that has the last element. An inductive form of this function clearly shows what must be added to calculate the value of f .

Now we can define our main function:

$$F : \mathbb{N} \longrightarrow \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{N}) \times \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{N});$$

$$\mathbb{N} \ni n \longrightarrow F(n) = \langle n, \{n\}, g(n) \rangle \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{N}) \times \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{N}).$$

The set $F(\mathbb{N})$ exists and contains images of all elements of \mathbb{N} – no less, no more.

Let $p_1(F(\mathbb{N})), p_2(F(\mathbb{N})), p_3(F(\mathbb{N}))$ be projections of the set $F(\mathbb{N})$ on axis – accordingly to definition of the function F .

Now we can examine these three sets:

- $p_1(F(\mathbb{N})) = i(\mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{N}$,
 - $p_2(F(\mathbb{N}))$ is the family of all one-element sets of $p_1(F(\mathbb{N}))$, so this is the family of all one-element sets of \mathbb{N} ,
 - Since all the three elements of each one ordered triple are created together or not at all, we have $n \in p_1(F(\mathbb{N})) \Leftrightarrow \{n\} \in p_2(F(\mathbb{N})) \Leftrightarrow g(n) \in p_3(F(\mathbb{N}))$. In particular: $\neg \exists \{n\} \in p_2(F(\mathbb{N})) \ g(n) \notin p_3(F(\mathbb{N}))$.
- This way $p_3(F(\mathbb{N}))$ must contain the sum of all elements of $p_2(F(\mathbb{N}))$. Thus

$$p_3(F(\mathbb{N})) \ni \bigcup p_2(F(\mathbb{N})) = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \{n\} = \mathbb{N}.$$

If so

$$\exists_{n_0 \in \mathbb{N}} F(n_0) = \langle n_0, \{n_0\}, \mathbb{N}, \rangle \in F(\mathbb{N}).$$

But all elements of $p_3(F(\mathbb{N}))$ have the last element. It means that the set \mathbb{N} – the set of all natural numbers – must have the last element.

- *Axiom of Infinity* is broken.

We can also ask what about $F(n_0 + 1)$. The number $n_0 + 1$ is the successor of n_0 , so it is a natural number and $F(n_0 + 1)$ exists. But $n_0 + 1 \notin \bigcup_{i=0}^{n_0} \{i\} = \mathbb{N}$. Then $p_3(F(\mathbb{N}))$ must contain the proper superset of \mathbb{N} that contains only natural numbers – and we get two different sets of all natural numbers.

- $\mathbb{N} \neq \mathbb{N}$ in the sens of *Axiom of Extentionality*.

3 Addendum

How to dismantle the set \mathbb{N} up to \emptyset by induction can be found in [3]. (Conclusions remain the same.)

4 Conclusions

In Zermelo's set of axioms the set of all natural numbers \mathbb{N} cannot exist. Z axioms, and also ZF , have a deeply rooted contradiction inside.

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References

- [1] Ebbinghaus Heinz-Dieter, Peckhaus Volker. *Ernst Zermelo – An Approach to His Life and Work*. Springer, 2007.
- [2] Moschovakis Yiannis. *Notes on Set Theory*. Springer, 2006.
- [3] Kopczyński Adam C. *The Set of All Natural Numbers in Ernst Zermelo's System of Axioms*. <https://zenodo.org/record/3529874> access: 2020-01-31